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**A STUDY OF THE PATTERN OF INTROVERSION/EXTRAVERSION AMONG
MALE HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENT**

Political science

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Abstract

The present was carried out to find out relation between introversion/Extraversion with academic Achievement among male high school students. A sample of 50 students were selected randomly for the present study. MPI (Mandsley personality inventory) Hindi version of Eyseric IEPI prepared by S.Jalota and S.D. Kapoor was used for the the study. The findings revealed that there is perfect positive co-relation between introversion and academic achievement that is if one varies another will also varies on the other side there is negative correlation between extroversion and the academic achievement that is if one increases other will increases. It may be permitted that introverts

will show better performance in educational tasks, and then the extroverts, Introverts do better at school and achieve high university grades. This setting of higher goal for prolonged period of time is essential in any long term programme of academic achievement.

Concept of personality

The most distinctive feature of any personality is his personality. This is the overall pattern of integration, intellectual ability, aptitudes and many other distinguishable characteristic, thus the term personality, refer to the whole individual. It is an important variable in most of the behaviour response and study of human behavior responses and study of human behavior is incomplete without the variable of personality. According to Broody (1972) the study of personality rests ultimately on the fact of individual differences. The true search for the understanding of individual differences, temperamental peculiarities and other deviations from the strictly average behavior i.e. personality can in a real sense be said to have a beginning with Hippo-crates and Galen. They identified four major temperamental types on the basis of humors melancholic, choleric, Sanguine and phlegmatic. These four types are supposed to be responsible for difference in behavior. Their physiological theory is also regarded as somewhat quaint, but the descriptive scheme is still used.

A solution to that problem was provided in the 19th century by Wundt who pointed out the four ways classification of Greeks could be accommodated by two independent and continuous variables of emotional response, strength of emotions and speed of change. What Wundt called speed of response is now usually labeled as extraversion and introversion (Wilson,1972)

Academic Achievement

Education is a process as well as a product, both maintaining an aspect of continuity ranging from the 'womb to tomb'. In a technical sense, John Dewey speaks of "Education as that reconstruction or reorganization of experiences which adds to the meaning of experience and which

increases ability to direct the course of subsequent experiences.” From the working point of view, education is often regarded as synonymous with learning and by educational evaluation; we measure the achievement of the learners.

Achievement is the performance in series of tests for a given skill or knowledge, usually academic. It is the outcome of general and specific learning experiences, which are assessed by the school authorities with the help of achievement tests, which may either be standardized or teacher-made. It also involves the appraisal by the student and the teacher of their success and failures from time to time with a view to continuous improvement so that education becomes dynamic and self-developing.

Sometimes achievement of a student is determined by an ‘Achievement Quotient’ (A.Q) which is expressed as a percentile ratio of the student. The achievement age is defined as the chronological age corresponding to any particular level on a scale of achievement. However, most test specialists now agree that A.Qs present a greatly oversimplified and often misleading basis for judging achievement. Academic achievement is also influenced by achievement motivation. The need that has attracted the greatest amount of attention has been the need to achieve. Thus academic achievement is also said to be important phases of life today. In this rapid advancement in science and technology the place of education has become so vital that every person works to educate his child.

Concept of academic achievement.

The academic achievement is day by day attracting the attention of the educator because it has been taken as criteria for selection in various walks of life. Achievement way of life is not determined by achievement, it is essentially directed by it, academic achievement is the attraction of some intellectual and personality actors.

Trow (1960) defines academic achievement as “the attained ability or degree of competence in school tasks, wholly measured by standardized tests and expressed in age grade units based on norms defined from a wide sampling of pupils performance academic achievement is the core of educational

growth academic achievement generally refers to the degree of level of success or that of proficiency attain in some specific area covering scholastic or academic work.

Factors influencing Academic Achievement

(a) **Cognitive factors:** Intellectual creativity

(B) **Non-Cognitive factor:** Includes personality variables self concept, Adjustment, study habits, interests, aspirations, needs, motivation and Anxiety.

(C) **Home Environment Factors:** Socio – economic status parental aspiration and expectation, parental attitude, methods of teaching, curriculum, emotional climate of the school etc.

(D) **Social Environment Factor:** Include teachers personality, curriculum, emotional climate of the school etc.

The **importance of academic achievement** lies in the fact that it sets an emotional tonic in one's life. Accordingly, achievement is the proficiency in performance in any skill or knowledge. In fact, academic achievement refers to the pupil's knowledge, attainment, and skills developed in the school/ college subjects, which are assessed by the authorities with the help of achievement test in the form of examination. Accordingly to **crow and crow (1963)**, achievement means the extent to which the learner is profiting from instruction in a given area of learning. **Good C.V. (1941)** in his "Dictionary of Education" has defined the achievement as "knowledge attained or skill development in school subjects usually designed by test scores or by marks assigned by the teacher or by both".

Stephens (1956) states, "Not that other aspect of educational objectives is to be ignored by the fact remains that academic achievement is the unique responsibility of all educational institutions established by the society to promote a wholesome scholastic development of the pupils."

Introversion and extroversion do not seem to be invariable attributes of individuals. An individual may show both introvert and extrovert tendencies in different situations. Hence, the idea of personality

dubbing an individual as an introvert or extrovert does not find favour with psychologists. Most of the really ambiverts.

An **introvert** is more interested in the inner world of thoughts and feelings than in the outer world of affairs and actions. He / she does not easily mix others; he is sensitive and is easily hurt.

The **extrovert** is interested in his environment; he is a practical man of action and enjoys mixing with others. He is not unduly sensitive and is prepared for the rough tumble of life.

Cattell (1956) and Guilford (1934) similar to Eysenck's Extraversion and Neuroticism extracted factors which closely resemble them. As regards the study of extraversion / Introversion and Neuroticism, **Eysenck (1964)** believe that it can be analyzed at two levels i.e. causative and descriptive.

Objectives

1. To administer Mandsley personality Inventory (MPI) the Hindi version of Eysenck personality Inventory (EPI) on Govt. High school male student.
2. To find out relation between introversion/Extraversion with academic Achievement.

The same for the present study was drawn from the male students of 9th and 10th classes of Govt. High school, Viyaypur, tehsil Jammu (J&K). A random sample of 50 male students was drawn for the study.

Tool

MPI (Mandsley personality inventory) Hindi version of H>J> Eysenck IEPI prepared by S.Jalota and S.D. Kapoor.

The Mandsley personality inventory (MPI) is a brief but standard as well as an easily administered and scored inventory which is designed for accessing introversion and extroversion dimension of personality. It is suitable for normal and abnormal adults and also for adolescents. The test

can be used as a group or an individual test. For a person of age of 15 and above. The vocabulary required is that of the average newspaper. Although no time limit is enforced in the testing. Each of these items is answerable by making a tick mark into one of the 3 boxes.

Procedure

After the selection of the sample Hindi version of EPI was given to each student and were request to read the instructions very carefully given on the first page of the inventory and then respond to the given items they were requested to given response to all the item.

Analysis and interpretations

	Mean	S.D.	Co-relation with academic achievement
Introverts	48.56	3.64	1.00
Extroverts	54.42	11.27	-0.90

Discussion

The present study was design to study the pattern of introversion/Extroversion amongst high school male students with their academic achievement. From the results it is clear that there is perfect positive co-relation between introversion and academic achievement that is if one varies another will also varies on the other side there is negative correlation between extroversion and the academic achievement that is if one increases other will increases. The deduction may be permitted that introverts will show better performance in educational tasks, and then the extroverts, Introverts do better at school and achieve high university grades. This setting of higher goal for prolonged period of time is essential in any long term programme of academic achievement.

Various other studies also support this concept that introverts found high on achievement motivation and show higher level of performance in a academic as compared to extroverts. Example

Lowell (1952) found that introverts are high on achievement motivation and showed a high level of performance on both mathematic and verbal tasks, Atkinson and Liturin (1960) found that subject high on achievement motivation, persisted 60% and performed 64% on examination as compared to the subject low on achievement motivation who persisted 32% and performed 32% on examination, wankowspi (1973) found that introverts had obtained better grades and secondary school and were likely to obtained a good degree at university.

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